

USAGE AND STYLISTIC FUNCTIONS OF ENTRIES

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ABSTRACT

The speaker perceives things and events, the nature of relations between them, events in different directions related to each other through his own power of thinking: he forms and expresses his opinion accordingly. In doing so, he selects and summarizes the important aspects of various relationships, connections, and various signs and situations in reality. He drops the unimportant ones or separates the important ones from others and shows them separately. As a result, all aspects of related things and events, all aspects of relations between them may not find their full expression in the speech. In the same process, the speaker feels the need to add something, to comment, to make the content of the speech that has been formed in his mind reach the listener fully, to be understandable. It is necessary to provide additional information about the basic idea, something that seems to be abstract, to make it concrete this necessity and need causes various explanations and additional information to be given in the structure of a ready-made sentence formed in the mind of the speaker-the use of inputs.

Key words: oral speech, written speech, applications, terms, inputs, phrases, grammatical relation, stylistic functions.

INTRODUCTION

The process of expressing an opinion is related to oral speech. However, it will not be enough to explain the occurrence of inputs by unprepared expression of opinion (oral speech) [1]. Because they can be used as a unique way of expressing an opinion in oral speech. It is more related to the situation of the speech, to whom the speech is addressed, the interlocutor's age and profession, the syntactic structure of the sentences in the text, their interrelationship, and the consistency of the content of the sentences in the text. The reasons for the use of introduction in written speech and fiction cannot be evaluated as the result of unprepared expression of opinion, inability to form the opinion correctly and clearly. Because the use of such inputs is a special way of expressing an opinion, used with a certain purpose, premeditated. Introductions in the literary language are used as a unique semantic-stylistic, syntactic tool, creating a great opportunity for the writer.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this article, scientific description of the use and stylistic functions of input constructions was given in a descriptive way. The exact solution of the main problem set before the research was determined by the method of distributive analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Words and phrases belonging to a special lexical layer, difficult to understand for many people, various names and terms are often found in the language of the press and fiction and are used for a specific stylistic purpose. Interpretation and explanation of the meaning of such words and phrases and additional information about them is often given in the form of entries. Sometimes it becomes difficult to determine the literary norm of doublet words, to demarcate the dialectal lexicon and the lexicon of the literary language. In such cases, the writer may hesitate to choose one of them and give one as an introduction.

Examples:

The servant was asked where there was a bathroom (murcha) in the near future (G.Gulam).

He grabbed four pieces of chachvan (chimmat) in his son's hand (G.Gulam).

This type of introduction is more common in works created in the 20s and 30s. because in this period, the lexicon of the literary language and the dialectal lexicon were not et clearly differentiated. Even now, it can be observed that such lexical units are used as a literary norm, and it is difficult to distinguish them from each other stylistically. Explaining the meaning of a word by citing its equivalent, variant is also related to the selection and use of terms in a scientific manner. Because the word chosen as a term can have multiple meanings or be used differently by different authors. In this case, it is necessary to limit the meaning expressed by them, to interpret and explain the essence of the terms used in different ways. Consequently, these types of introductions also serve to popularize and define one of the terms as a norm in the creation of the norm of the Uzbek literary language and national terminology. Such entries are functionally similar to detached comments or footnotes. They can be removed from the sentence structure and given at the bottom of the page using a link. In this case, there will be no change in the syntactic structure of the main sentence: it will retain its grammatical integrity. However, it is more convenient to explain the meanings of words with the help of entries than at the bottom of the page. Because in artistic and scientific-popular texts, it should not distract the attention of the reader from the speech fragment, but allow to interpret it along the way.

Introductions allow the reader to show the details to be told, the writer's position, his reaction to the events directly in the speech, while the event is happening. However, it is not advisable to use introductions more than necessary in speech. It can also make the statement difficult to understand. The introduction of entries into the text in inappropriate and unnecessary places makes the speech

structurally complicated, weakens its effectiveness, and annoys the reader.

If the use of input units is subordinated to a certain goal from the logical and stylistic point of view, it serves to clearly and vividly express the idea with all its shades. It is understood that entries do not always consist of secondary comments and additional information. Often, they state important and necessary facts about the general content direction, stylistic character of the sentence. But they will be relegated to the background. This is also a unique way of distinguishing, attracting the reader's attention: facilitates the joint understanding of the content of the introduction with the main sentence. Hence, introductions help to deliver great content and impact in a compact medium. In this case, the main sentence plays the role of a necessary content for the full understanding of the content of the input: it enables the use of the input in a simple and concise form. The introduction is to inform the reader about the object being described, but the details that the reader needs to know (when appropriate), as well as to comment on the meaning of certain words or phrases in the character's speech, it also helps to interpret the meaning of certain words or phrases in the character's speech, thereby clearly showing the character of the character. Examples:

- *He cried that he had pressed everything he found alone. No. Whatever I looted (he didn't have the language to say "stole"), I gave the imam, the judge, the centurion, and the amin. They were aware of everything. Once, when I slaughtered a farmer's ox (I didn't have the language to say "I stole" again), my judge uncle said, "Wretched, what do you do to your neighbor!" If you take a job in the next village, a little further away, will you be able to get a hand on your feet!" those who saved them. I certainly did not waste these kindnesses, I took away two foxes from a hunter (by stealing, no asking for them).*

The writer is showing the true meaning (in what sense) of the words chosen by the character. The speaker may have difficulty in choosing a word or

expression, he may hesitate. This often causes pauses and stops in the speech. The same pauses related to the choice of words and emotions in the character's speech are revealed with the help of inputs. Such introductions play a special role in illuminating the inner world, mood, and feelings of the characters.

The writer through the inputs in the process of storytelling and description addresses the reader directly, his feelings, this incident describes his view on: he mediates between the reality of the past and the present reality, as if he builds a bridge between them. These types of introductions help to draw the reader into a conversation and connect with him.

CONCLUSION

So, the meanings expressed by the input constructions are diverse, and their semantic types are certainly not limited to the ones indicated above. Also, input constructions are not only a means of expressing various comments and additional information, but are also widely used for certain stylistic purposes as a special way of expressing ideas.

REFERENCES

1. А.Н.Гвоздев. Современный русский литературный язык, ч. II, синтаксис, М., Учпедгиз, 1961, стр. 193.
2. А.И.Ефимов. Стилистические функции скобок в языке Салтыкова Шедрина ("Русский язык в школе", 1946, № 1, стр. 25-33).
3. Л.П.Григорьева. Вставные конструкции в романе Л.Н.Толстого "Война и мир" (Сб.: "Вопросы изучения русского языка", Алма-Ата, Изд-во АН КазССР, 1955, стр. 275-299).
4. Н.В.Юстратова. Функции вставных конструкций в языке публицистики ("Ученые записки Кишиневского госуниверситета", т. 71, Вопросы общего русского языкознания, Кишинев, 1964, стр. 130-134).

5. Ю.М.Златополский, Ф.Шварцман. Стилистические функции вставных конструкций в работе В.И.Ленина и Г.В.Плеханова – “Тезисы конференции Кишиневского госуниверситета” (1964), Кишинев, 1965, стр. 264-267.
6. Т.Р.Котляр. Вставочные конструкции в современном английском языке, Саратов, изд. Саратовского госуниверситета, 1962, стр. 14.
7. И.А.Бабакова. Явление вводности в русском языке, Харьков, 1955.
8. И.Тошалийев. Ҳозирги ўзбек адабий тилида киритма конструкциялар. Ўзбекистон ССР “ФАН” Нашриёти Тошкент – 1976